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METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF HYDRALAZINE HYDROCHLORIDE BY USING UV AND RP-HPLC

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ABSTRACT

A simple, rapid, precise and highly selective spectrophotometric method was developed for estimation of Hydralazine Hydrochloride in tablet dosage form. This method, involves the measurement of absorbances of Hydralazine at the wavelength of 262nm. Distilled water was used as solvent. Linearity was observed in the concentration range of 2-20 μ g/ml. The accuracy of the method was found to be 99.2%. The LOD and LOQ of Hydralazine was found to be 0.051 μ g/ml and 0.16 μ g/ml. The method showed good reproducibility and recovery with % RSD less than 2. A selective, precise, isocratic and accurate reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method was developed for the determination of Hydralazine Hydrochloride in the tablet dosage form. A chromatographic separation was achieved on reverse phase BDS Hypersil C18 column (250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ). The mobile phase consists of mixture of Methanol and Acetonitrile. The flow rate was 1.2ml/min and the effluents were monitored at the wavelength of 270nm. The retention time of Hydralazine HCl was found to be 2.58min respectively. Hydralazine HCl was found to be linear in the range of 0.5 to 4 μ g/ml with the recoveries of 98 % and 100.5 %. The method was validated as per ICH guidelines. In proposed methods good results were obtained and can be applied for the routine analysis of formulation.

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INTRODUCTION

Hydralazine HCl is a vasodilator, works by relaxing blood vessels (arterioles) and increasing the supply of blood and oxygen to the heart while reducing its workload. It also functions as an antioxidant. Hydralazine in combination with Isosorbide dinitrate is used in the treatment of Angina.

In view of need for developing the new analytical method in the quality control laboratories for routine analysis of Hydralazine HCl in formulations, the present work aims to develop simple and accurate instrumental methods for estimation of Hydralazine HCl and extend it for its determination in formulation and in laboratory prepared synthetic mixture.

MATERIALS AND INSTRUMENTS

a) Pure drug samples

The drug samples of Hydralazine Hydrochloride was purchased at Orbit Scientific Products, Secunderbad

b) Chemicals and solvents used

Acetonitrile : HPLC grade, Qualigens Fine Chemicals, Mumbai
HPLC water : Qualigens Fine Chemicals, Mumbai.
Methanol : HPLC grade, Qualigens Fine Chemicals, Mumbai.

c) Instruments

- Shimadzu Digital Electronic Balance- BL 220H.
- Lab India SAB 5000, pH meter.
- Value Vaccum pump.
- Ultrasonic cleaner, Life care equipments pvt.ltd
- Shimadzu UV-1800, UV/Vis-Spectrophotometer.
- Shimadzu HPLC, BDS Hypersil C18 column, UV detector.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF UV SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF HYDRALAZINE HYDROCHLORIDE IN PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS

Selection of Wavelength and Solvent:

In order to find out the wavelength of maximum absorption of the drug, a solution of the drug was prepared in water and scanned using UV spectrophotometer within the wavelength region of 200-400 nm against water as blank. The absorption curve showed absorption maxima at 262nm, hence this wavelength was fixed for analysis.

Fig: 1. UV spectrum of standard Hydralazine in water at 262nm.

Linearity:

Linearity of Hydralazine HCl was found in the concentration range of 2-20 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. The absorbances of these solutions were detected at wavelength 262nm respectively.

Fig: 2 : Calibration graph of Hydralazine Hydrochloride at 262nm.

Precision:

Intraday Precision and Interday Precision studies were carried out by analysis of standard drug solutions at two different concentrations in the linearity range for three times on the same day and over a period of one week. %RSD was calculated.

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantitation

The LOQ and LOD values found to be 0.16 μ g/ml and 0.051 μ g/ml.

Recovery studies

In order to ensure the suitability and reliability of the method, recovery studies were carried out. To an equivalent quantity of formulation powder (10mg), a known quantity of standard Hydralazine Hydrochloride was added at 50% and 100% level and the contents were re-analysed by the proposed method.

Table: 1: Recovery studies.

Level	%Recovery	%RSD
50%	99.4%	0.64%
100%	99.9%	0.40%

ANALYSIS OF FORMULATION

Twenty tablets (APRESOLINE) were powdered and the average weight was calculated. A quantity equivalent to 10 mg of drug was dissolved in water and the volume was made up to get a working concentration of 4 μ g/ml each of Hydralazine Hydrochloride was noted at 262nm.

Table: 2: Analysis of formulation.

Drug	Amount (mg/tab)		% label claim	% RSD*
	Labelled	Found		
Hydralazine	10mg	9.7mg	100.8%	0.21%

DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF HYDRALAZINE HYDROCHLORIDE BY USING RP-HPLC IN BULK AND PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS.

Reverse phase chromatographic technique is selected since the drug is polar in nature

Selection of Mobile phase:

For developing RP – HPLC method, different mobile phase systems with different ratios were tried, among which methanol and acetonitrile at 270nm gave symmetrical peaks with good resolution (Rt-2.58) and hence fixed for further studies.

Fig: 4: Methanol : Acetonitrile(40:60v/v).

FIXED CHROMATOGRAPHIC CONDITIONS

Stationary Phase	: BDS Hypersil, C18 Column, (250 x 4.6 mm , 5 μ)
Mobile phase	: Methanol and Acetonitrile
Solvent ratio	: 40:60
Detection wavelength	: 270nm
Flow rate	: 1.2 ml/ml
Operating Pressure	: 42 kgf
Operating Temperature	: Room Temperature
Injection volume	: 20 μ l
Mode of operation	: Isocratic elution

Linearity and Range

Linearity was found in the range of 0.5 – 4 μ g/ml working standards of drug. Calibration graphs were plotted using peak areas of standard drugs vs. concentration of standard drug solutions.

Fig: 5: Calibration graph of Hydralazine HCl by RP-HPLC.

Precision

Precision of method was demonstrated by

- Intraday precision
- Inter day precision

Intraday precision and Interday precision were found out by carrying out analysis of standard drug solutions at two different concentrations in the linearity range for three times on the same day and over a period of week and % RSD was calculated.

Table: 3. Intraday Precision.

Level	Concentration	Peak area	%RSD
1	2 μ g	80197	0.29%
		80589	
		80623	
2	2.5 μ g	104485	0.66%
		103269	
		103295	

Table: 4. Inter day precision.

Level	Concentration	Peak area	%RSD
1	2 μ g	80469	0.72%
		81582	
		81369	
2	2.5 μ g	103683	0.29%
		104981	
		103361	

Accuracy

To study the accuracy of the method, recovery studies were carried out. To an equivalent quantity of formulation powder (10mg) a known quantity of standard Hydralazine was added to 50% and 100% level extracted with mobile phase and made up to mark with same. This solution was further diluted. The concentration of drugs present in resulting solution was determined using assay method and percentage recovery and % RSD were calculated.

Table: 5. Recovery Studies.

Level	%Recovery	%RSD
50%	99.9%	0.40%
100%	99.4%	0.64%

* RSD of three Observations.

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

The LOD and LOQ of Hydralazine HCl was found to be 0.029 μ g/ml and 0.06 μ g/ml and respectively.

ANALYSIS OF FORMULATION

Twenty tablets (APRESOLINE) were powdered and the average weight was calculated. A quantity equivalent to 10 mg of drug was dissolved in mobile phase. Finally the volume was made up to a mark to get a working standard of 1 μ g/ml each of Hydralazine Hydrochloride.

Table: 6. Analysis of Formulation.

Drug	Label claim(mg)	Amount found(mg)	%Label claim	%RSD
Hydralazine	10mg	9.8mg	100.4%	1.02%

CONCLUSION

The direct UV method development for the analysis of Hydralazine Hydrochloride can be applied for the routine analysis of formulation.

The developed HPLC method offer's research work related to new method development and was found satisfactory, simple, precise, accurate with good resolution, shorter retention time. In proposed method symmetrical peaks were obtained.

The low LOD and LOQ values in this method is suitable in quality control. The less retention time obtained in this method reduces the run time and enhances the use of the method.

However, all these methods can be used for the analysis of Hydralazine HCl in formulation.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

LOD	:	Limit of Detection
LOQ	:	Limit of Quantitation
%RSD	:	Relative Standard Deviation
RP-HPLC	:	Reverse Phase Liquid Chromatography

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